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THE RELATIONSHIP OF HUMAN HEALTH WITH THE QUALITATIVE COMPOSITION OF WATER

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Annotation: The data on the influence of the characteristics of the qualitative composition of water on human health have been studied. In the course of the analysis, comparative – evaluative, search methods were used. The quality of drinking water was monitored. It has been established that the qualitative composition of water has an effect on the human body. Since systematically consuming water containing harmful substances in quantities exceeding permissible, their negative impact affects human health.

Keywords: water, qualitative composition, monitoring, human health, maximum permissible concentrations

Relevance. In terms of importance for humans, water takes second place after oxygen. It participates in the regulation of body temperature, humidification of air during breathing, delivery of nutrients and oxygen to all cells, protection and functioning of vital organs, digestion of food, excretion of metabolic products from the body. Water is the basis of acid-base balance; it is necessary for a person to maintain a water-electrolyte balance [1, 2].

WHO has proven that drinking water can be not just a food product, but also a source of macro- and microelements necessary for the body, and with the right approach, physiologically complete drinking

water can make up for the deficiency of essential substances with improper nutrition, contribute to the prevention of hypertension, cardiomyopathy and other diseases, as well as the recovery of the body after intense physical exertion and high ambient temperature [3-5].

Since poor-quality drinking water can be a cause and a risk factor for the development of a number of serious diseases, the population should show a high level of competence on this issue and effectively use the knowledge gained in their pra in the future [6-8].

The purpose of the study. To study the data on the influence of the characteristics of the qualitative composition of water on human health.

Materials and methods of research. In the course of the analysis, comparative evaluation and search methods were used, literary data, already existing developments in this field, physiological values of the main macro- and microelements were taken into account, the quality of drinking water was monitored.

The results of the study and their discussion. Drinking water supplied to the population must comply with hygienic safety requirements, its quality is controlled by the Republican Center for Hygiene, Epidemiology and Public Health and the organization that provides water supply.

One of the factors that determines the quality of water is the source from which it is taken. The presence of harmful impurities can be caused both by the ingress of substances resulting from human economic activity into it, and by the natural composition of water.

The main problems that determine the quality of drinking water in our country are: increased content of iron and manganese in water from underground sources, increased content of nitrogen-containing compounds (nitrates, nitrites, ammonium compounds) in water, microbiological contamination of well water, causing turbidity and color of water.

The high content of iron and manganese is a property of Belarusian groundwater, which is associated with exceeding the standard for iron content (normally 0.3 mg/l). This problem is typical for half of the water intake wells in our country. The increased iron content in the

water gives it a brown color and a characteristic metallic taste. Such water leaves traces on literally everything. Even with the smallest iron content in the water, it leaves rusty spots on any surface. The consequences for the body occur with a higher concentration of iron and manganese: according to WHO, with an iron content of up to 2 mg / l (average value), the majority of people can use it without health problems. In our country, they are trying to solve this problem with the construction of de-ironing stations. Despite the fact that a sufficient number of stations have already been built in the republic, water with a high iron content is still supplied to the population in many localities, especially small ones. In domestic conditions, iron is removed with the simplest filters.

Water hardness is another criterion by which water quality is assessed. Depending on the hardness, the water can be soft, medium hardness, hard and very hard. In persons with sensitive thin skin, hard water causes blockage of the ducts of the sebaceous glands of the skin and leads to painful dryness and irritation. Stiffness also affects changes in protein-lipid and water-salt metabolism.

The use of very soft water adversely affects human health. Scientific data indicate that when it is used, there are disturbances in the conduction of nerve impulses in the heart muscle, the frequency and severity of the course of cardiovascular diseases (coronary heart disease, arterial hypertension, the frequency of myocardial infarction) increases. There is an assumption about the role of water hardness in the development of urolithiasis. The hardness of water for drinking purposes is limited to a concentration of 7 mmol/l.

Pollution of drinking water with nitrogen-containing compounds (nitrates, nitrites, ammonium ions) for decentralized water supply is relevant for our country. This problem mainly concerns water intake wells and wells supplying water from shallow aquifers in rural areas.

The content of nitrates in water is much more dangerous than their content in vegetables and fruits. Increased nitrate content in water causes toxic cyanosis. Nitrates react with hemoglobin in the blood and deprive red blood cells of the ability to saturate the body's cells with oxygen. This leads to metabolic disorders, decreased immunity, as well as to the disease of methemoglobinemia, in which the blood completely

loses its ability to carry oxygen to tissues and organs. The hygienic standard for the content of nitrates is no more than 45 mg / liter.

Conclusions. As a result of the analysis, it was found that the qualitative composition of water has a powerful effect on the human body. Since systematically consuming water containing harmful substances in quantities exceeding permissible, their negative impact affects human health.

Bibliography

[1] Scientific article «Approaches to substantiation and development of hygienic criteria for assessing the physiological usefulness of water intended for consumption by the population» [Electronic resource]. – URL: <http://elib.grsmu.by/bitstream/handle/files/23444/79-82z.pdf?sequence=1>. (date of access: 13.06.2023).

[2] Pivovarov Yu.P. Hygiene and fundamentals of human ecology / Yu.P. Pivovarov, V.V. Koralik, L.S. Zinevich. – Minsk: «Academy», 2008. 528 p.

[3] Zimatkina T.I. Radiation medicine: a workshop for students studying in the specialties 1-79 01 01 «Medical business», 1-79 01 02 «Pediatrics» / T.I. Zimatkina, A.S. Aleksandrovich. – Grodno: GrSMU, 2021. 174 p.

[4] Zimatkina T.I. Ecological medicine = Ecological Medicine: a manual for students of the Faculty of foreign students with the English language of instruction studying in the specialty 1-79 01 01 «Medical business» / T.I. Zimatkina, A.S. Aleksandrovich. – Grodno: GrSMU, 2020. 212 p.

[5] Radiation medicine: a study method. manual / A.N. Stozharov [et al.]. // 3rd ed. – Minsk: BSMU, 2007. 144 p.

[6] Republican Unitary Enterprise «Scientific and practical center of hygiene» [Electronic resource]. – URL: <https://rspch.by>. (date of access: 13.06.2023).

[7] Zimatkina T.I. Valeology: a textbook for students of institutions of higher education in the specialty «Nursing» / T.I. Zimatkina, A.S. Aleksandrovich. – Grodno: GrSMU, 2020. 296 p. Vulture RIDGE.

[8] Sanitary norms and rules. «Sanitary and epidemiological requirements for centralized drinking water supply systems», approved by Resolution No. 69 of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Belarus on 16.09.2014.

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